

Reaction of Ketene Dithioacetals with Aziridine. A New Synthesis of *N*-Vinylaziridines and their Iodide Ion-assisted Rearrangement to Pyrrolines

M. V. BASAVESWARA RAO^a, J. R. SURESH^a, ARVIND KUMAR^a, H. ILA^{b*} and H. JUNJAPPA^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong-793 003

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur-208 016

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The ketene dithioacetals **1**, **4**, **9** and **11** react readily with aziridine **2** to give the corresponding *N*-vinylaziridines **3**, **5**, **8** and **12** respectively, which on iodide ion-catalyzed rearrangement undergo ring expansion to give pyrrolines **14**, **18**, **21** and **22** respectively.

The isomerization of aziridine derivatives has been extensively examined to develop synthetic routes for a variety of heterocyclic systems^{1,2}. For example, *N*-acyl-, *N*-aroyl-aziridines and their thio analogs have been shown to undergo rearrangements to oxazolines, oxazepins, and thiazolines³⁻⁵. These *N*-acylaziridines are among the earliest systems which were examined for their rearrangement to yield ring-expanded heterocycles. Recently, a number of papers have appeared in the literature on *N*-substituted-2-vinylaziridines and their rearrangements to tetrahydropyridines⁶⁻⁹, azepins¹⁰, pyrrolines¹¹, and open-chain products^{12,13}. Surprisingly, the corresponding *N*-vinylaziridines have not been studied extensively¹⁴ apparently because of their labile nature and difficulty in their preparation, although a few reports are there on rearrangement of 1,2-divinylaziridines to azepins¹⁰. Recently, Lindstrom and Somfai¹⁵ have reported 3,3-Claisen rearrangement of 1,2-divinylaziridines to 7-membered lactams involving *in situ* generation of *N*-vinyl functionality. In a preliminary communication we have shown that *N*-vinylaziridines are readily prepared in high yields by reacting ketene dithioacetals with aziridine which when treated with potassium iodide, undergoes rearrangement to the corresponding pyrrolines. We describe in this paper, a detailed account of the preparation of various *N*-vinylaziridines and their subsequent iodide ion-catalyzed rearrangement to pyrrolines.

Results and Discussion

***N*-Vinylaziridines** : Polarized ketene dithioacetals are known to undergo facile displacement reactions with amines to give the corresponding *S,N*-acetals¹⁷. A similar reaction of these intermediates with strained 3-membered ring aziridine is of particular interest as they would yield *N*-vinylaziridines which might serve as precursors for interesting class of heterocycles by subsequent rearrangement involving ring expansion. Thus when doubly activated ketene dithioacetal (**1a**) was reacted with aziridine (**2**) in diethyl ether, the corre-

sponding *N*-vinylaziridine (**3a**) was obtained in 87% yield (Scheme 1). Similarly the other ketene dithioacetals (**1b-d**) were reacted with **2** under the described reaction conditions

Scheme 1

to yield the corresponding *N*-vinylaziridines (**3b-d**) in 70–89% overall yields. The α -oxoketene dithioacetals (**4a-f**) derived from pyrazolones also behaved in the same way as shown in Scheme 2. Thus the *N*-vinylaziridines (**5a-f**) were obtained in quantitative yields by reacting aziridine with **4a-f** in diethyl ether.

In a similar reaction, when singly activated ketene dithioacetal (**6a**) was reacted with aziridine in refluxing

- $$\begin{array}{ll} \text{4, 5a, } & \text{R}^3 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \\ \text{b, } & \text{R}^3 = \text{p-MeC}_6\text{H}_4 \\ \text{c, } & \text{R}^3 = \text{p-MeOC}_6\text{H}_4 \\ \text{d, } & \text{R}^3 = \text{p-ClC}_6\text{H}_4 \\ \text{e, } & \text{R}^3 = \text{p-BrC}_6\text{H}_4 \\ \text{f, } & \text{R}^3 = \text{CH}_3 \end{array}$$

Scheme 2

benzene, the acetal (6a) was recovered unchanged. However, when the reaction was carried out in a sealed tube at 165° for 24 h, the *S,N*-acetal (7) was formed exclusively instead of 8 (Scheme 3). Apparently the displaced gaseous MeSH which was held compressed in the sealed tube acted as a powerful nucleophile and cleaved the labile aziridine ring to yield *S,N*-acetal (7).

Scheme 3

Spitzner *et al.*¹⁸ demonstrated that singly activated α -oxoketene dithioacetals (6) can be quaternized by treating them with dimethyl sulfate and perchloric acid to yield the corresponding dimethylsulfonium perchlorates (9) which were reacted with methanol to yield the corresponding *O,S*-acetals. This reaction was successfully exploited in our laboratory to prepare a number of *O,S*-acetals (10) by reacting 9 with various alcohols and phenols¹⁹ (Scheme 3). Based on these facile reactions of 9 with alcohols and phenols, it was contemplated that the perchlorate salts could well be reacted with amines to yield the corresponding *S,N*-acetals under mild conditions. Thus when dimethylsulfonium perchlorate (9a) was reacted with aziridine in the presence of potassium carbonate in dry THF the corresponding *S,N*-acetal was obtained in 60% yield, the ¹³C nmr spectrum of which showed the presence of both *Z* (8a) and *E* (8'a) isomers in the ratio 17 : 3. The reaction of 9b and 9c with aziridine similarly yielded the corresponding *S,N*-acetals 8b and 8c as a mixture of *Z* and *E* isomers respectively. The sulfonium perchlorate salt of tetralone mercaptal (11) similarly reacted with 2 to yield the corresponding *S,N*-acetal (12) in 54% yield (Scheme 4).

Iodide ion-catalyzed rearrangement of vinylaziridines (3a-d, 5a-f, 8a-c and 12) : The vinylaziridines thus prepared

Scheme 4

were next examined for rearrangement under both thermal and iodide ion-catalyzed conditions. In a typical experiment, a mixture of vinylaziridine (3a) and potassium iodide in dry acetone was stirred at room temperature for 2 h and after workup the corresponding pyrroline (14a) was obtained in 85% yield (Scheme 5). Similarly, 3b yielded 14b in 80% yield whereas 3c underwent simultaneous deacetylation during rearrangement to yield the corresponding 3-carbomethoxy-2-(methylthio)pyrroline (14c). However, the attempted isomerization of vinylaziridine (3d) failed to undergo the observed rearrangement to yield the corresponding pyrroline, instead led to only polymeric products. The reaction mixture under thermal conditions (refluxing benzene, toluene, or xylene) also ended into polymeric products.

Scheme 5

The *S,N*-acetals of pyrazolones (5) were considered of interest since they could rearrange to either the corresponding oxazepins (17) or the spirocompounds (18) (Scheme 6). However, when 5a was treated with KI as described earlier, it yielded the corresponding spiro-compound (18a) in 80% yield and no traces of oxazepin (17a) was detected in the reaction mixture. Similarly, 5b-f afforded the corresponding spirocompounds 18b-f in 74–80% overall yields. Isomerization of 5 under thermal conditions also led to the formation of the corresponding spiro-compounds 18 exclusively in poor yields.

Scheme 6

The other vinylaziridines (**8a-c**) when treated with KI in acetone yielded the corresponding 2-methylthio-3-arylpyrrolines (**21a-c**) in 62–69% overall yields (Scheme 7). The vinylaziridine derived from tetralone mercaptal (**12**) under similar reaction conditions yielded the spiro-compound (**22**) in 47% yield.

Scheme 7

The possible mechanism for KI-assisted rearrangement is depicted in Schemes 5, 6 and 7. It is a two-step reaction sequence involving the initial ring opening by nucleophilic iodide ion followed by ring closure by elimination of iodide ion to afford the observed pyrrolines.

In conclusion, it has been demonstrated that doubly acti-

vated ketene dithioacetals react with aziridine to yield the corresponding vinylaziridines in excellent yields. The less activated α -oxoketene dithioacetals also on activation through quaternization react with aziridine to yield the vinylaziridines as a mixture of *Z* and *E* isomers. The vinylaziridines thus prepared were shown to undergo iodide ion-catalyzed rearrangement to yield the corresponding pyrrolines in good yields. The scope of this method is apparently governed by the ease with which aziridine can react with ketene dithioacetals to give the required *N*-vinylaziridines without the strained three-membered ring being destroyed. The further synthetic applications of these interesting intermediates are being continued.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on Townson & Mercer and Thomas Hoover apparatus (capillary methods) and are uncorrected. IR spectra were obtained on Perkin-Elmer 137 and 983 spectrophotometers, nmr spectra on Varian A-60D (60 MHz), EM-390 (90 MHz) and Bruker ACF-300 (300 MHz) spectrometers using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra on Hitachi RMU-6E and Jeol D-300 spectrometers. Elemental analysis were carried out on a Heraeus CHN-analyzer.

The ketene dithioacetals were prepared according to the reported procedures¹⁷.

All the compounds prepared were characterized by physical, spectral and analytical data. Compounds **3** and **5** were analyzed only for nitrogen since they partially decomposed during purification. All the compounds showed molecular ion peaks in their mass spectra.

General procedure for the reaction of aziridine with ketene dithioacetals (1a-d and 4a-f). Preparation of N-vinylaziridines (3a-d and 5a-f): Aziridine (50 mmol) was added to an ice-cold solution of ketene *S,S*-acetal (10 mmol) in dry diethyl ether (150 ml) and the mixture was stirred with cooling (0–5°) for 2 h and then at room temperature (1 h, monitored by tlc). Nearly half of the solvent was removed under vacuum and the solid separated was filtered off and washed with ether. In the case of **1c**, the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 12 h and after removal of the solvent under reduced pressure, the product **3c** was obtained as viscous liquid.

1-(N-Aziridino)-2-carbethoxy-2-cyano-1-(methylthio)ethylene (3a): White needles (acetone-ether) (87%), m.p. 96° (Found: N, 12.96. C₉H₁₂N₂O₂S (212.27) calcd for: N, 13.20%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 2195, 1680 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (60 MHz; CDCl₃) 1.31 (3H, t, OCH₂CH₃), 2.56 (3H, s, SCH₃), 2.70 (4H, br s, aziridino), 4.25 (2H, q, OCH₂CH₃).

2-Amido-1-(N-aziridino)-2-cyano-1-(methylthio)ethylene (3b): White needles (acetone-ether) (89%), m.p. 105–06° (Found: N, 22.96. C₇H₉N₃OS (183.23) calcd. for: N,

22.93%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3390, 3310, 3275, 2180, 1655, 1628, 1575 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (60 MHz; DMSO- d_6) 2.38–4.71 (7H, br m, SCH_3 and aziridino).

1-(N-Aziridino)-2-acetyl-2-carbethoxy-1-(methylthio)ethylene (3c): Viscous liquid (70%) (Found: N, 6.02. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3\text{S}$ (229.30) calcd. for: N, 6.11%); ν_{\max} (neat) 1685, 1638 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (60 MHz; CDCl_3) 1.35 (3H, t, OCH_2CH_3), 2.25 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.35 (4H, s, aziridino), 2.48 (3H, s, SCH_3), 4.28 (2H, q, OCH_2CH_3).

1-(N-Aziridino)-2,2-dicyano-1-(methylthio)ethylene (3d): White needles (acetone-ether) (85%), m.p. 109° (Found: N, 25.26. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{S}$ (165.22) calcd. for: N, 25.43%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 2195 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (60 MHz; CDCl_3) 2.68 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.75 (4H, s, aziridino).

4-[N-Aziridinomethylthio)methylene]-1,3-diphenyl-5-oxo- Δ^2 -pyrazoline (5a): Orange solid (ether) (96%), m.p. 111–13° (Found: N, 12.32. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{OS}$ (335.43) calcd. for: N, 12.53%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1654, 1580 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (60 MHz; CDCl_3) 2.16 (4H, s, aziridino), 2.65 (3H, s, SCH_3), 7.13–7.83 (8H, m, ArH), 8.13 (2H, m, ArH).

4-[N-Aziridinomethylthio)methylene]-3-(p-methylphenyl)-5-oxo-1-phenyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline (5b): Orange solid (ether) (97%), m.p. 115° (Found: N, 11.86. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{OS}$ (349.46) calcd. for: N, 12.02%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1645 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (60 MHz; CDCl_3) 2.20 (4H, s, aziridino), 2.41 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.66 (3H, s, SCH_3), 7.16–7.75 (7H, m, ArH), 8.18 (2H, m, ArH).

4-[N-Aziridinomethylthio)methylene]-3-(p-methoxyphenyl)-5-oxo-1-phenyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline (5c): Orange solid (ether) (81%), m.p. 122–23° (Found: N, 11.26. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$ (365.45) calcd. for: N, 11.50%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1648 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (60 MHz; CDCl_3) 2.19 (4H, s, aziridino), 2.63 (3H, s, SCH_3), 3.86 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.80–7.76 (7H, m, ArH), 8.16 (2H, m, ArH).

4-[N-Aziridinomethylthio)methylene]-3-(p-chlorophenyl)-5-oxo-1-phenyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline (5d): Orange solid (ether) (94%), m.p. 134° (Found: N, 11.14. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{ClN}_3\text{OS}$ (369.87) calcd. for: N, 11.36%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1650 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (60 MHz; CDCl_3) 2.20 (4H, s, aziridino), 2.63 (3H, s, SCH_3), 7.11–7.75 (7H, m, ArH), 8.06 (2H, m, ArH).

4-[N-Aziridinomethylthio)methylene]-3-(p-bromophenyl)-5-oxo-1-phenyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline (5e): Orange solid (ether) (96%), m.p. 145–46° (Found: N, 9.88. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{BrN}_3\text{OS}$ (414.32) calcd. for: N, 10.14%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1645 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (60 MHz; CDCl_3) 2.16 (4H, s, aziridino), 2.62 (3H, s, SCH_3), 7.10–7.66 (7H, m, ArH), 8.05 (2H, m, ArH).

4-[N-Aziridinomethylthio)methylene]-3-methyl-5-oxo-1-phenyl- Δ^2 -pyrazoline (5f): Orange solid (ether) (54%), m.p. 119–20° (Found: N, 15.42. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{OS}$ (273.36) calcd. for: N, 15.37%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1645 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (60 MHz; CDCl_3) 2.43 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.63 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.76 (4H, br s, aziridino), 7.06–7.56 (3H, m, ArH), 7.98 (2H, m, ArH).

Reaction of 6a with aziridine. Preparation of 3-methylthio-3-(2-methylthioethylamino)-1-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (7): A mixture of 6a (0.01 mol) and aziridine (0.05 mol) in dry benzene (20 ml) was heated in a steel bomb at 165° for 24 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina using hexane-benzene (3 : 2) as eluent: viscous liquid (60%), (Found: C, 58.11; H, 6.08; N, 5.01. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{NOS}_2$ (267.3) calcd. for: C, 58.36; H, 6.35; N, 5.23%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3400, 1585, 1550 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (60 MHz; CDCl_3) 2.15 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.45 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.73 (2H, t, CH_2SCH_3), 3.61 (2H, m, NHCH_2), 5.70 (1H, s, vinylic), 7.43 (5H, m, ArH), 12.06 (1H, br s, NH).

General procedure for the reaction of aziridine with dimethylsulfonium perchlorate salts (9a-c and 11). Preparation of N-vinylaziridines (8a-c and 12): To a well-stirred suspension of potassium carbonate (100 mmol) in dry tetrahydrofuran (50 ml) at ice-cold temperature, aziridine (50 mmol) in dry THF (5 ml) was added at once and stirring was continued at the same temperature for 15 min. Perchlorate salt 9 or 11 (25 mmol) was added to the reaction mixture slowly pinchwise over a period of 0.5 h and stirring continued for another 3 h (monitored by tlc). Potassium carbonate was filtered off from the reaction mixture, solvent removed under reduced pressure, and the residue obtained was chromatographed over neutral alumina using hexane-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) as eluent.

3-(N-Aziridino)-3-methylthio-1-phenyl-2-propen-1-one (8a): Yellow needles (acetone-ether) (61%), m.p. 85–86° (Found: C, 65.56; H, 5.92; N, 6.36. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{NOS}$ (219.31) calcd. for: C, 65.72; H, 5.97; N, 6.39%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1606 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (300 MHz; CDCl_3) 2.26 (4H, br s, aziridino), 2.44 (3H, s, SCH_3), 6.57 (1H, s, vinylic H), 7.40–7.73 (3H, m, ArH), 7.89 (2H, m, ArH); ^{13}C nmr δ (75 MHz; CDCl_3) (Z isomer) 13.88, 30.53, 103.87, 127.38, 128.26, 131.46, 139.24, 174.29, 187.72; (E isomer) 15.55, 32.70, 101.20, 127.53, 128.26, 131.37, 140.30, 172.94, 184.78.

3-(N-Aziridino)-1-(p-methoxyphenyl)-3-methylthio-2-propen-1-one (8b): Yellow needles (acetone-ether) (68%), m.p. 84–85° (Found: C, 62.83; H, 6.02; N, 5.65. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$ (249.33) calcd. for: C, 62.62; H, 6.06; N, 5.62%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1592, 1492 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (300 MHz; CDCl_3) 2.28 (4H, br s, aziridino), 2.46 (3H, s, SCH_3), 3.79 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.55 (1H, s, vinylic H), 6.88 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, ArH), 7.88 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, ArH); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz; CDCl_3) (Z isomer) 13.92, 30.52, 55.29, 103.80, 113.45, 129.52, 132.01, 162.28, 173.29, 186.69; (E isomer) 15.57, 32.68, 55.29, 101.28, 113.44, 129.67, 132.96, 162.28, 171.80, 183.86.

3-(N-Aziridino)-1-(p-chlorophenyl)-3-methylthio-2-propen-1-one (8c): Light yellow needles (acetone-ether) (64%), m.p. 80–82° (Found: C, 57.08; H, 4.69; N, 5.58.

$C_{12}H_{12}NOSCl$ (253.75) calcd. for: C, 56.80; H, 4.77; N, 5.52%; ν_{max} (KBr) 1612, 1510 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (90 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 2.36 (4H, br s, aziridino), 2.53 (3H, s, SCH_3), 6.60 (1H, s, vinylic H), 7.48 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, ArH), 8.01 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, ArH).

2-[(N-Aziridinomethylthio)methylene]-3,4-dihydro-naphthalen-1-one (12): Light yellow needles (acetone-ether) (54%), m.p. 134–35° (Found: C, 68.38; H, 6.20; N, 5.65. $C_{14}H_{15}NOS$ (245.34) calcd. for: C, 68.54; H, 6.16; N, 5.71%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1608, 1500 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (90 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 2.43 (4H, br s, aziridino), 2.50 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.96 (4H, br s, $(CH_2)_2$), 7.23–7.73 (3H, m, ArH), 8.25 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, ArH).

General procedure for the iodide ion-catalyzed isomerization of 3a-d, 5a-f, 8a-c and 12: A mixture of *S,N*-acetal (0.01 mol) and potassium iodide (0.02 mol) in dry acetone (150 ml) was stirred at 20° for 2 h (monitored by tlc). Acetone was removed under reduced pressure, the residue obtained was treated with water, and then extracted with dichloromethane. The organic layer was washed with water, dried over Na_2SO_4 , solvent distilled off, and the product was purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina using hexane-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluent. In the case of 3c, the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 10 h and then refluxed for 1 h. In the case of 5, the products were separated as white solid when the reaction mixture was treated with water and filtered off and purified by crystallization.

3-Carboethoxy-3-cyano-2-(methylthio)- Δ^1 -pyrroline (14a): Light yellow oil (85%), b.p. 155°/1 mm Hg (Found: C, 50.64; H, 5.90; N, 12.96. $C_9H_{12}N_2O_2S$ (212.27) calcd. for: C, 50.92; H, 5.70; N, 13.20%); ν_{max} (neat) 2225, 1740 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (60 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 1.35 (3H, t, OCH_2CH_3), 2.50 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.73 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.28 (4H, m, NCH_2 and OCH_2CH_3 overlapping).

3-Amido-3-cyano-2-(methylthio)- Δ^1 -pyrroline (14b): White crystals (acetone) (80%), m.p. 125–26° (Found: C, 45.64; H, 4.76; N, 22.79. $C_7H_9N_3OS$ (183.24) calcd. for: C, 45.88; H, 4.95; N, 22.93%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3380, 3285, 3155, 2228, 1650, 1610, 1600 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (60 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 2.53 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.80 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.11 (2H, t, NCH_2), 6.60 (2H, br s, $CONH_2$).

3-Carboethoxy-2-(methylthio)- Δ^1 -pyrroline (14c): Light yellow oil (45%), b.p. 105–08°/1 mm Hg (Found: C, 51.54; H, 6.79; N, 7.19. $C_8H_{13}NO_2S$ (187.26) calcd. for: C, 51.31; H, 7.00; N, 7.48%); ν_{max} (neat) 1700 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (60 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 1.28 (3H, t, OCH_2CH_3), 2.05–2.70 (5H, m, CH_2 and SCH_3 overlapping), 3.30 (1H, m, H-3), 4.11 (4H, m, NCH_2 and OCH_2CH_3 overlapping).

1,3-Diphenyl-6-methylthio-2,3,7-triazaspiro[4.4]non-1,6-dien-4-one (18a): White needles (acetone-ether) (80%), m.p. 144° (Found: C, 68.30; H, 5.15; N, 12.69. $C_{19}H_{17}N_3OS$ (335.43) calcd. for: C, 68.03; H, 5.11; N, 12.53%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1697 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (60 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 2.52 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.74 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.45 (2H, m, NCH_2), 7.57–8.12 (10H, m, ArH).

1-(*p*-Methylphenyl)-6-methylthio-3-phenyl-2,3,7-triazaspiro[4.4]non-6-dien-4-one (18b): White needles (acetone-ether) (80%), m.p. 145–46° (Found: C, 68.63; H, 5.62; N, 11.95. $C_{20}H_{19}N_3OS$ (349.46) calcd. for: C, 68.74; H, 5.48; N, 12.02%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1700 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (60 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 2.40 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.50 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.72 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.45 (2H, m, NCH_2), 7.49–8.12 (9H, m, ArH).

1-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-6-methylthio-3-phenyl-2,3,7-triazaspiro[4.4]non-1,6-dien-4-one (18c): White needles (acetone-ether) (74%), m.p. 130–31° (Found: C, 65.39; H, 5.32; N, 11.39. $C_{20}H_{19}N_3O_2S$ (365.45) calcd. for: C, 65.73; H, 5.24; N, 11.50%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1700 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (60 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 2.48 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.71 (2H, m, CH_2), 3.83 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.38 (2H, m, NCH_2), 7.33–8.11 (9H, m, ArH).

1-(*p*-Chlorophenyl)-6-methylthio-3-phenyl-2,3,7-triazaspiro[4.4]non-1,6-dien-4-one (18d): White needles (acetone-ether) (75%), m.p. 139–40° (Found: C, 61.35; H, 4.28; N, 11.54. $C_{19}H_{16}ClN_3OS$ (369.87) calcd. for: C, 61.70; H, 4.36; N, 11.36%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1698 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (60 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 2.50 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.69 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.41 (2H, m, NCH_2), 7.50–8.01 (9H, m, ArH).

1-(*p*-Bromophenyl)-6-methylthio-3-phenyl-2,3,7-triazaspiro[4.4]non-1,6-dien-4-one (18e): White needles (acetone-ether) (78%), m.p. 159–60° (Found: C, 54.85; H, 4.06; N, 9.91. $C_{19}H_{16}BrN_3OS$ (414.33) calcd. for: C, 55.08; H, 3.89; N, 10.14%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1690 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (60 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 2.50 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.67 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.41 (2H, m, NCH_2), 7.50–8.01 (9H, m, ArH).

1-Methyl-6-methylthio-3-phenyl-2,3,7-triazaspiro[4.4]non-6-dien-4-one (18f): White needles (acetone-ether) (78%), m.p. 80–82° (Found: C, 61.32; H, 5.41; N, 15.43. $C_{14}H_{15}N_3OS$ (273.36) calcd. for: C, 61.51; H, 5.53; N, 15.37%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1692 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (60 MHz; $CDCl_3$) 2.09 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.41 (3H, s, SCH_3), 2.53 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.26 (2H, m, NCH_2), 7.45–7.98 (5H, m, ArH).

3-Benzoyl-2-methylthio- Δ^2 -pyrroline (21a): Yellow viscous liquid (69%) (Found: C, 66.08; H, 5.83; N, 6.52. $C_{12}H_{13}NOS$ (219.31) calcd. for: C, 65.72; H, 5.97; N, 6.39%); ν_{max} (CCl_4) 3480, 1695, 1600 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (90 MHz; CCl_4) 2.36 (5H, br s, CH_2 , SCH_3), 3.83–4.26 (2H, m, NCH_2), 4.67 (1H, t, J 7.5 Hz, NH, exchangeable with D_2O), 7.39–7.73 (3H, m, ArH), 7.93–8.16 (2H, m, ArH).

3-(*p*-Methoxybenzoyl)-2-methylthio- Δ^2 -pyrroline (21b): Yellow viscous liquid (62%) (Found: C, 62.91; H, 6.01; N, 5.68. $C_{13}H_{15}NO_2S$ (249.33) calcd. for: C, 62.62; H, 6.06; N, 5.62%); ν_{max} (CCl_4) 3340, 1685 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr δ (90 MHz; CCl_4) 2.36 (5H, br s, CH_2 , SCH_3), 3.89 (5H, br s, NCH_2 , OCH_3), 4.65 (1H, t, J 7.5 Hz, NH, exchangeable with D_2O), 6.06 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, ArH), 7.16 (2H, d, J 9 Hz, ArH).

3-(*p*-Chlorophenyl)-2-methylthio- Δ^2 -pyrroline (21c): Yellow viscous liquid (69%) (Found: C, 56.96; H, 4.71; N, 5.42. $C_{12}H_{12}ClNOS$ (253.75) calcd. for: C, 56.80; H, 4.77; N,

5.52%), ν_{\max} (CCl₄) 3420, 1683 cm⁻¹, ¹H nmr δ (90 MHz, CCl₄) 2.39 (5H, br s, CH₂, SCH₃), 3.86–4.19 (2H, m, NCH₂), 4.67 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz, NH, exchangeable with D₂O), 7.50 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, ArH), 8.03 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, ArH)

3,4-Dihydronaphthalen-1-one-2-spiro-2'-aza-1'-(methylthio)cyclopent-1-ene (22) Yellow needles (47%), m p 138–39° (Found C, 68.40, H, 6.09, N, 5.68 C₁₄H₁₅NOS (245.34) calcd for C, 68.54, H, 6.16, N, 5.71%), ν_{\max} (KBr) 1652, 1608 cm⁻¹, ¹H nmr δ (90 MHz, CCl₄) 1.36–1.66 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.46 (3H, s, SCH₃), 2.73–3.29 (6H, m, CH₂, NCH₂), 7.19–7.70 (3H, m, ArH), 8.18 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, ArH)

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